

Recommended Iridium SBD dataformats for buoys

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The present document describes a list of dataformats which should be used to report buoy observations through Iridium SBD. These dataformats are the results of experiences got within the DBCP Iridium Pilot Project.

Version 1.1: Addition of dataformats #021 (high resolution SVP-BS), #031 (new buoys fitted with a thermistor chain) and #032 (same but for sea ice).

Version 1.2: Addition of dataformat #002 (sea ice SVP-B).

Version 1.3: Addition of dataformat#033 and #034 (new SVP-BTC types). Removing of dataformats #001 and #030.

Version 1.4: Addition of dataformat#022 (new SVP-BS reporting conductivity). Removing of dataformats #031 and #032. Update of table of section 3 (describing reported Iridium and GPS technical parameters).

Version 1.5: Addition of dataformat#003 (SVP-B with internal physical parameters), #080 (**temporary** format for SIO SVP-B drifters => not standard) and #090 (**draft** for high sampled HRSST data).

Version 1.6: Revision of dataformat#022 (SVP-BS reporting conductivity, renamed SVP-BSC) which had never been implemented, with increased accuracy for SST to 0.001 K and SSS to 0.001 psu.

Version 1.7: Addition of dataformat#091 (SVP with Barometer and Reference Sensor for Temperature, SVP-BRST)

Version 1.8: Addition of dataformat#092 (SVP-BRST with 1 Hz sampling); Fixed typo in dataformat#022.

1. Common characteristics

Each dataformat starts with a 8-bit identifier which characterizes the type of the buoy: SVP-B drifter with or without GPS, SVP-BS drifter (salinity), SVP-BTC drifter (fitted with a thermistor chain), basic Ice buoy... Another dataformat should be drawn for the SVP-BW drifter (Wind).

The format identifier is followed by the observation timestamp (year, month, day, hour, minute), then by basic measurements carried out by SVP-B drifters (air pressure, SST, barometer tendency, submergence – or strain gauge – count, battery voltage).

Then, two technical parameters are reported. Although the first should be the Iridium transmission duration in seconds, the second parameter is left in manufacturer's hands (see § 3).

Excepted for the SVP-B drifters which are not fitted with a GPS¹, the next block of all other dataformats contains the GPS position, its age (time delay) in minutes, as well as a couple of technical parameters which are left in manufacturer's hands (see § 3).

Important:

It is recommended to fill up the rooms of missing parameters with all bits to "1" excepted for the GPS position. In case a GPS fix is not available at the observation time, the previous position is reported with its time delay in minutes (reference is the time of observation for the other parameters). In case the most recent position is older than 4094 minutes, 4095 is reported in the message (i.e. all bits fitted to "1").

In order to save energy on drifting buoys, GPS fixes may be get less frequently than other parameters (e.g. every three hours instead of hourly). The GPS fix time delay is then different from zero. On ships, GPS fixes must be get at the same time than observed parameters.

2. List of dataformats

Ident.	Page	Platform type
000	3	SVP-B
001		<i>SVP-B without GPS – No longer suitable</i>
002	4	SVP-B (sea ice version)
003	5	SVP-B with internal technical parameters
004-019		<i>Reserved for buoys</i>
020	6	SVP-BS (salinity drifter) – Should no longer be used
021	7	SVP-BS (high resolution salinity drifter)
022	8	SVP-BSC (salinity drifter reporting conductivity)
023-029		<i>Reserved for buoys</i>
030		<i>SVP-BTC (thermistor chain) – No longer used</i>
031		<i>SVP-BTC-v2 – No longer used</i>
032		<i>SVP-BTC-v2 (sea ice version) – No longer used</i>
033	9	SVP-BTC-v3
034	11	SVP-BTC-v3 (sea ice version)
035-039		<i>Reserved for buoys</i>
040	12	Basic Ice Buoy
041-049		<i>Reserved for buoys</i>
050		SVP-BW (WOTAN buoy – <i>to be designed</i>)
051-079		<i>Reserved for buoys</i>
080	13	SVP-B made by SIO (temporary format – waiting for #003)
082-089		<i>Reserved for buoys (temporary dataformats)</i>
090	14	EUMETSAT SVP-B with two SST and one hydrostatic pressure buoys plus optional high frequency data (<i>draft</i>)
091	15	SVP-BRST (SVP with Barometer and Reference Sensor for Temperature)
092	16	SVP-BRST with 1Hz data
093-099		<i>Reserved for buoys (high frequency measurements)</i>
100-199		<i>Reserved (see Iridium dataformats for ships)</i>
200-255		<i>Reserved</i>

¹ The Iridium position is used instead.

Format #000 - SVP-B
(20 bytes)

Parameter	Bits	Pos	Offset	Max	Formula
Format identifier	8	0	0	254	Forced to 0 in present version
Year	7	8	2000	2126	Year = n + 2000
Month	4	15	0	12	Month = n
Day	6	19	0	31	Day = n
Hour	5	25	0	23	Hour = n
Minute	6	30	0	59	Minute = n
Air pressure	11	36	850.0	1054.6	AP (hPa) = n*0.1 + 850
SST	12	47	-5.00	35.94	SST (°C) = n*0.01 - 5
Pressure tendency	9	59	-25.5	25.5	dP (hPa) = n*0.1 - 25.5
Submergence/gauge count	6	68	0	100	Subm. (%) = n * 1.6129
Battery voltage	6	74	5	17.4	Vbat (V) = n*0.2 + 5
1 st Tech. parameter (Iridium)	8	80	0	254	See § 3
2 nd Tech. parameter	8	88	0	254	See § 3
GPS fix time delay	12	96	0	4094	Delay (min) = n
GPS Latitude	20	108	-90	90	Lat (deg) = n*0.0002 - 90
GPS Longitude	21	128	-180	180	Lon (deg) = n*0.0002 - 180
3 rd Tech. parameter (GPS)	7	149	0	126	See § 3
4 th Tech. parameter (GPS)	4	156	0	14	See § 3

Format #002 - SVP-B with GPS (sea ice version)
(20 bytes)

Parameter	Bits	Pos	Offset	Max	Formula
Format identifier	8	0	0	254	Forced to 2 in present version
Year	7	8	2000	2126	Year = n + 2000
Month	4	15	0	12	Month = n
Day	6	19	0	31	Day = n
Hour	5	25	0	23	Hour = n
Minute	6	30	0	59	Minute = n
Air pressure	11	36	900.0	1104.6	AP (hPa) = n*0.1 + 900
SST	12	47	-25.0	15.94	SST (°C) = n*0.01 - 25
Pressure tendency	9	59	-25.5	25.5	dP (hPa) = n*0.1 - 25.5
Submergence/gauge count	6	68	0	100	Subm. (%) = n * 1.6129
Battery voltage	6	74	5	17.4	Vbat (V) = n*0.2 + 5
1 st Tech. parameter (Iridium)	8	80	0	254	See § 3
2 nd Tech. parameter	8	88	0	254	See § 3
GPS fix time delay	12	96	0	4094	Delay (min) = n
GPS Latitude	20	108	-90	90	Lat (deg) = n*0.0002 - 90
GPS Longitude	21	128	-180	180	Lon (deg) = n*0.0002 - 180
3 rd Tech. parameter (GPS)	7	149	0	126	See § 3
4 th Tech. parameter (GPS)	4	156	0	14	See § 3

Format #003 - SVP-B with internal technical parameters

(23 bytes) – Should become the new standard for SVP, SBP-B, and their sea-ice variants

Parameter	Bits	Pos	Offset	Max	Formula
Format identifier	8	0	0	254	Forced to 3 in present version
Year	7	8	2000	2126	Year = n + 2000
Month	4	15	0	12	Month = n
Day	6	19	0	31	Day = n
Hour	5	25	0	23	Hour = n
Minute	6	30	0	59	Minute = n
Air pressure	12	36	800.0	1209.4	AP (hPa) = n*0.1 + 800
SST	14	48	-80.00	83.82	SST (°C) = n*0.01 – 80
Strain gauge count	6	62	0	100	SGC (%) = n * 1.6129
Battery voltage	6	68	5	17.4	Vbat (V) = n*0.2 + 5
Iridium transm. duration	6	74	0	310	SBDT (s) = n*5
Iridium retries	3	80	0	6	SBDR = n
GPS time delay (since last fix)	12	83	0	4094	Delay (min) = n
GPS Latitude (deg. N)	21	95	-90	90	Lat (deg) = n*0.0001 - 90
GPS Longitude (deg. E)	22	116	-180	180	Lon (deg) = n*0.0001 - 180
GPS Horiz. Dilution of Precision	7	138	0	12.6	HDOP = n*0.1
GPS #sat	5	145	0	30	Nsat = n
GPS Time To First Fix (TTFF)	9	150	0	510	TTFF (s) = n
Hull Humidity	8	159	0	100	Hum (%) = n*0.5
Hull Pressure	8	167	900	1408	Press (hPa) = n*2 + 900
Hull Temperature	9	175	-80.0	175	Temp (°C) = n*0.5 – 80

Format #020 - SVP-BS (salinity)
(24 bytes)

Parameter	Bits	Pos	Offset	Max	Formula
Format identifier	8	0	0	254	Forced to 20 in present version
Year	7	8	2000	2126	Year = n + 2000
Month	4	15	0	12	Month = n
Day	6	19	0	31	Day = n
Hour	5	25	0	23	Hour = n
Minute	6	30	0	59	Minute = n
Air pressure	11	36	850.0	1054.6	AP (hPa) = n*0.1 + 850
SST	12	47	-5.00	35.94	SST (°C) = n*0.01 - 5
Pressure tendency	9	59	-25.5	25.5	dP (hPa) = n*0.1 - 25.5
CT temperature ²	12	68	-5.00	35.94	CT_temp (°C) = n*0.01 - 5
Salinity	12	80	15.00	55.94	SSS (psu) = n*0.01 + 15
CT sensor error	1	92	0	1	Err = n
Submergence/gauge count	6	93	0	100	Subm. (%) = n*1.6129
Battery voltage	6	99	5	17.4	Vbat (V) = n*0.2 + 5
1 st Tech. parameter (Iridium)	8	105	0	254	See § 3
2 nd Tech. parameter	8	113	0	254	See § 3
GPS fix time delay	12	121	0	4094	Delay (min) = n
GPS Latitude	20	133	-90	90	Lat (deg) = n*0.0002 - 90
GPS Longitude	21	153	-180	180	Lon (deg) = n*0.0002 - 180
3 rd Tech. parameter (GPS)	7	174	0	126	See § 3
4 th Tech. parameter (GPS)	4	181	0	14	See § 3
Spare (unused)	7	185			All bits forced to « 1 »

²

Sea temperature measured by the conductivity sensor

Format #021 - High resolution SVP-BS (salinity)
(24 bytes)

Parameter	Bits	Pos	Offset	Max	Formula
Format identifier	8	0	0	254	Forced to 21 in present version
Year	7	8	2000	2126	Year = n + 2000
Month	4	15	0	12	Month = n
Day	6	19	0	31	Day = n
Hour	5	25	0	23	Hour = n
Minute	6	30	0	59	Minute = n
Air pressure	11	36	850.0	1054.6	AP (hPa) = n*0.1 + 850
SST	12	47	-5.00	35.94	SST (°C) = n*0.01 - 5
Pressure tendency	9	59	-25.5	25.5	dP (hPa) = n*0.1 - 25.5
CT temperature ³	16	68	-5.00	60.534	CT_temp (°C) = n*0.001 - 5
Salinity	15	84	15.00	47.766	SSS (psu) = n*0.001 + 15
CT sensor error	1	99	0	1	Err = n
Submergence/gauge count	6	100	0	100	Subm. (%) = n*1.6129
Battery voltage	6	106	5	17.4	Vbat (V) = n*0.2 + 5
1 st Tech. parameter (Iridium)	8	112	0	254	See § 3
2 nd Tech. parameter	8	120	0	254	See § 3
GPS fix time delay	12	128	0	4094	Delay (min) = n
GPS Latitude	20	140	-90	90	Lat (deg) = n*0.0002 - 90
GPS Longitude	21	160	-180	180	Lon (deg) = n*0.0002 - 180
3 rd Tech. parameter (GPS)	7	181	0	126	See § 3
4 th Tech. parameter (GPS)	4	188	0	14	See § 3

³

Sea temperature measured by the conductivity sensor

Format #022 - SVP-BSC (salinity/conductivity)
(26 bytes)

Parameter	Bits	Pos	Offset	Max	Formula
Format identifier	8	0	0	254	Forced to 22 in present version
Year	7	8	2000	2126	Year = n + 2000
Month	4	15	0	12	Month = n
Day	6	19	0	31	Day = n
Hour	5	25	0	23	Hour = n
Minute	6	30	0	59	Minute = n
Air pressure	11	36	850.0	1054.6	AP (hPa) = n*0.1 + 850
SST	12	47	-5.00	35.94	SST (°C) = n*0.01 - 5
Pressure tendency	9	59	-25.5	25.5	dP (hPa) = n*0.1 - 25.5
CT temperature ⁴	16	68	-5.00	60.534	CT_temp (°C) = n*0.001 - 5
CT conductivity	16	84	0	65.53	CT_cond (mS/cm) = n*0.001
Salinity	15	100	15	47.77	SSS (psu) = n*0.001 + 15
CT sensor error	1	115	0	1	Err = n
Submergence/gauge count	6	116	0	100	Subm. (%) = n*1.6129
Battery voltage	6	122	5	17.4	Vbat (V) = n*0.2 + 5
1 st Tech. parameter (Iridium)	8	128	0	254	See § 3
2 nd Tech. parameter	8	136	0	254	See § 3
GPS fix time delay	12	144	0	4094	Delay (min) = n
GPS Latitude	20	156	-90	90	Lat (deg) = n*0.0002 - 90
GPS Longitude	21	176	-180	180	Lon (deg) = n*0.0002 - 180
3 rd Tech. parameter (GPS)	7	197	0	126	See § 3
4 th Tech. parameter (GPS)	4	204	0	14	See § 3

⁴ Sea temperature measured by the conductivity sensor

Format #033 - SVP-BTC (version 3)
(variable length)

Parameter	Bits	Pos	Offset	Max	Formula
Format identifier	8	0	0	254	Forced to 33 in present version
Year	7	8	2000	2126	Year = n + 2000
Month	4	15	0	12	Month = n
Day	6	19	0	31	Day = n
Hour	5	25	0	23	Hour = n
Minute	6	30	0	59	Minute = n
Air pressure	11	36	900.0	1104.6	AP (hPa) = n*0.1 + 900
SST	12	47	-5	35.94	SST (°C) = n*0.01 - 5
Pressure tendency	9	59	-25.5	25.5	dP (hPa) = n*0.1 - 25.5
Air temperature	10	68	-60.0	42.2	AT (°C) = n*0.1 - 60
Submergence/gauge count	6	78	0	100	Subm. (%) = n*1.6129
Battery voltage	6	84	5	17.4	Vbat (V) = n*0.2 + 5
1 st Tech. parameter (Iridium)	8	90	0	254	See § 3
2 nd Tech. parameter	8	98	0	254	See § 3
GPS fix time delay	12	106	0	4094	Delay (min) = n
GPS Latitude	20	118	-90	90	Lat (deg) = n*0.0002 - 90
GPS Longitude	21	138	-180	180	Lon (deg) = n*0.0002 - 180
3 rd Tech. parameter (GPS)	7	159	0	126	See § 3
4 th Tech. parameter (GPS)	4	166	0	14	See § 3
Number of temp. probes	5	170	0	30	NbT = n
Depth indicator	1	175	0	1	Di = n
Depth of temp. probe T1	9	176	0	255	DT1 (m) = n*0.5
Temp. of probe T1	12	185	-5	35.94	T1 (°C) = n*0.01 - 5
Depth of temp. probe T2	9	197	0	255	DT2 (m) = n*0.5
Temp. of probe T2...	12	206	-5	35.94	T2 (°C) = n*0.01 - 5
...					
Number of press. probes	3		0	6	NbP = n
Pressure of probe P1... ⁵	15		0	327.66	P1 (dbar) = n*0.01
...					

Differences with regards to dataformat #031 are:

- an offset of 900 hPa instead of 850 hPa for air pressure;
- the addition of a room for air temperature;
- the addition of one-bit parameter to tell if the depths are computed (0) or nominal (1);
- an increase of the resolution for subsurface sensors and depths.

The length of the message is equal to:

$$(22.375 \text{ bytes} + \text{NbT} * 2.625 \text{ bytes} + \text{NbP} * 1.875 \text{ byte})$$

⁵ Subsurface pressure values are reported in decibar here (1 dbar = 10⁴ Pa). The atmospheric pressure must be removed to compute the depths of hydrostatic pressure probes. One decibar corresponds on one metre depth, approximately.

... where NbT is the number of temperature probes and NbP is the number of pressure probes. For instance:

- the length of the message for a buoy having 17 temperature probes and three pressure sensors will be 73 bytes;
- the length of the message for a buoy having 11 temperature probes and one pressure sensor will be 54 bytes;

By default, the depth of each temperature probe is provided by the buoy (indicator = 0). In case this is not possible, its nominal position (distance from the buoy) is given instead (indicator = 1).

Format #034 - SVP-BTC (version 3 - Sea ice version)
(variable length)

Parameter	Bits	Pos	Offset	Max	Formula
Format identifier	8	0	0	254	Forced to 34 in present version
Year	7	8	2000	2126	Year = n + 2000
Month	4	15	0	12	Month = n
Day	6	19	0	31	Day = n
Hour	5	25	0	23	Hour = n
Minute	6	30	0	59	Minute = n
Air pressure	11	36	900.0	1104.6	AP (hPa) = n*0.1 + 900
SST	12	47	-20	20.94	SST (°C) = n*0.01 - 20
Pressure tendency	9	59	-25.5	25.5	dP (hPa) = n*0.1 - 25.5
Air temperature	10	68	-60.0	42.2	AT (°C) = n*0.1 - 60
Submergence/gauge count	6	78	0	100	Subm. (%) = n*1.6129
Battery voltage	6	84	5	17.4	Vbat (V) = n*0.2 + 5
1 st Tech. parameter (Iridium)	8	90	0	254	See § 3
2 nd Tech. parameter	8	98	0	254	See § 3
GPS fix time delay	12	106	0	4094	Delay (min) = n
GPS Latitude	20	118	-90	90	Lat (deg) = n*0.0002 - 90
GPS Longitude	21	138	-180	180	Lon (deg) = n*0.0002 - 180
3 rd Tech. parameter (GPS)	7	159	0	126	See § 3
4 th Tech. parameter (GPS)	4	166	0	14	See § 3
Number of temp. probes	5	170	0	30	NbT = n
Depth indicator	1	175	0	1	Di = n
Depth of temp. probe T1	9	176	0	255	DT1 (m) = n*0.5
Temp. of probe T1	12	185	-20	20.94	T1 (°C) = n*0.01 - 20
Depth of temp. probe T2	9	197	0	255	DT2 (m) = n*0.5
Temp. of probe T2...	12	206	-20	20.94	T2 (°C) = n*0.01 - 20
...					
Number of press. probes	3		0	6	NbP = n
Pressure of probe P1...	15		0	327.66	P1 (dbar) = n*0.01
...					

The difference with regards to dataformat #033 is a lower range for sea temperatures. The length of the message - which is variable -, is the same.

Format #040 - Basic Ice Buoy
(21 bytes)

Parameter	Bits	Pos	Offset	Max	Formula
Format identifier	8	0	0	254	Forced to 40 in present version
Year	7	8	2000	2126	Year = n + 2000
Month	4	15	0	12	Month = n
Day	6	19	0	31	Day = n
Hour	5	25	0	23	Hour = n
Minute	6	30	0	59	Minute = n
Air pressure	11	36	850.0	1054.6	AP (hPa) = n*0.1 + 850
Hull temperature	10	47	-60.0	42.2	HT (°C) = n*0.1 - 60
Pressure tendency	9	57	-25.5	25.5	dP (hPa) = n*0.1 - 25.5
Air Temperature	10	66	-60.0	42.2	AT (°C) = n*0.1 - 60
Battery voltage	6	76	5	17.4	Vbat (V) = n*0.2 + 5
1 st Tech. parameter (Iridium)	8	82	0	254	See § 3
2 nd Tech. parameter	8	90	0	254	See § 3
GPS fix time delay	12	98	0	4094	Delay (min) = n
GPS Latitude	20	110	-90	90	Lat (deg) = n*0.0002 - 90
GPS Longitude	21	130	-180	180	Lon (deg) = n*0.0002 - 180
3 rd Tech. parameter (GPS)	7	151	0	126	See § 3
4 th Tech. parameter (GPS)	4	158	0	14	See § 3
Spare (unused)	6	162			All bits forced to « 1 »

Format #080 - SIO SVP-B drifters
(23 bytes)

Parameter	Bits	Pos	Offset	Max	Formula
Format identifier	8	0	0	254	Forced to 80 in present version
Year	7	8	2000	2126	Year = n + 2000
Month	4	15	0	12	Month = n
Day	6	19	0	31	Day = n
Hour	5	25	0	23	Hour = n
Minute	6	30	0	59	Minute = n
Air pressure	11	36	850.0	1054.6	AP (hPa) = n*0.1 + 850
SST	12	47	-5.00	35.94	SST (°C) = n*0.01 - 5
Pressure tendency	9	59	-25.5	25.5	dP (hPa) = n*0.1 - 25.5
Strain gauge count	6	68	0	100	SGC (%) = n * 1.6129
Battery voltage	6	74	5	17.4	Vbat (V) = n*0.2 + 5
Iridium transmit duration	6	80	0	310	SBTD (s) = n*5
Iridium retries	2	86	0	2	SBTR = n
Hull internal humidity	3	88	2	86	IHum (%) = n*14 + 2
Hull internal pressure	5	91	900	1200	IPress (hPa) = n*10 + 900
GPS fix time delay	12	96	0	4094	TTFF (s) = n
GPS Latitude	20	108	-90	90	Lat (deg) = n*0.0002 - 90
GPS Longitude	21	128	-180	180	Lon (deg) = n*0.0002 - 180
GPS HDOP ⁶	7	149	0	12.6	HDOP = n*0.1
Nb of GPS satellites	4	156	0	14	Nsat = n
Hull internal temperature	8	160	-25.5	25.3	ITemp (°C) = n*0.2 - 25.5
GPS Time To First Fix (TTFF)	16	168	0	65534	TTFF (s) = n

⁶ HDOP : Horizontal Dilution Of Precision

Format #090 - SVP-B with two SST probes and one hydrostatic pressure sensors (Eumetsat), plus optional high frequency data

Draft - (26.5 to about 1490 bytes)

Parameter	Bits	Pos	Offset	Max	Formula
Format identifier	8	0	0	254	Forced to 90 in present version
Year	7	8	2000	2126	Year = n + 2000
Month	4	15	0	12	Month = n
Day	6	19	0	31	Day = n
Hour	5	25	0	23	Hour = n
Minute	6	30	0	59	Minute = n
Air pressure	11	36	900.0	1104.6	AP (hPa) = n*0.1 + 900
Air pressure tendency	9	47	-25.5	25.5	dP (hPa) = n*0.1 - 25.5
Analog SST	12	56	-5.00	35.94	SST (°C) = n*0.01 - 5
Digital SST (mean)	16	68	-5.000	60.534	SST (°C) = n*0.001 - 5
Hydrostatic press. (mean)	12	84	0	20.470	pHydr (dbar) = n*0.005
Digital SST (sd)	12	96	0	4.094	SST Sd (°C) = n*0.001
Hydrostatic pressure (sd)	11	108	0	10.230	pHydr Sd (dbar) = n*0.005
Submergence/gauge count	6	119	0	100	Subm. (%) = n * 1.6129
Battery voltage	6	125	5.0	17.4	Vbat (V) = n*0.2 + 5
1 st Tech. parameter (Iridium)	8	131	0	254	See § 3
2 nd Tech. parameter	8	139	0	254	See § 3
GPS fix time delay	12	147	0	4094	Delay (min) = n
GPS Latitude	20	159	-90	90	Lat (deg) = n*0.0002 - 90
GPS Longitude	21	179	-180	180	Lon (deg) = n*0.0002 - 180
3 rd Tech. parameter (GPS)	7	200	0	126	See § 3
4 th Tech. parameter (GPS)	4	207	0	14	See § 3
High Frequency bloc presence indicator	1	211	0	1	
Nb. of samples	9	212	0	300	NbS = n
Digital SST obs 1	16	221	-5.000	60.534	SST (°C) = n*0.001 - 5
Hydrostatic pressure obs 1	12	237	0	20.47	pHydr (dBar) = n*0.005
Air pressure obs 1	11	249	900.0	1104.6	AP (hPa) = n*0.1 + 900
Digital SST obs 2	16	260	-5.000	60.534	SST (°C) = n*0.001 - 5
Hydrostatic pressure obs 2	12	276	0	20.47	pHydr (dBar) = n*0.005
Air pressure obs 2	11	288	900.0	1104.6	AP (hPa) = n*0.1 + 900
...					

The length of the message is equal to (27.625 bytes + NbS * 4.875 bytes). For 60 samples at 1 Hz, the message will be 320.125 bytes long (i.e. equivalent to eleven 30-byte invoiced blocks). For a five-minute sample, the data can be sent through 5 consecutive SBD messages, or sent in one single message with appropriate Iridium transceiver allowing up to 1960 bytes SBD message size.

Important remark: note this dataformat has not been yet adopted. Modifications has still to be made before implementation.

Format #091 - SVP-BRST (SVP with Barometer and Reference Sensor for Temperature)

(30 bytes)

Parameter	Bits	Pos	Offset	Slope	Max	Formula
Format identifier	8	0	0	1	254	Forced to 91
Year	7	8	2000	1	2126	Year = n + 2000
Month	4	15	0	1	12	Month = n
Day	6	19	0	1	31	Day = n
Hour	5	25	0	1	23	Hour = n
Minute	6	30	0	1	59	Minute = n
Air pressure	12	36	800.0	0.1	1209.4	AP (hPa) = n*0.1 + 800
Analog SST	12	48	-5.00	0.01	35.94	SST (°C) = n*0.01 - 5
Digital SST (mean)	16	60	-5.000	0.001	60.534	HRSST Mean (°C) = n*0.001 - 5
Digital SST 10th percentile	12	76	-5.00	0.01	35.94	HRSST (°C) P10 = n*0.01 - 5
Digital SST 10th to 30th percentiles range	8	88	0.00	0.01	2.54	HRSST (°C) P30-P10 = n*0.01
Digital SST 30th to 50th percentiles range	8	96	0.00	0.01	2.54	HRSST (°C) P50-P30 = n*0.01
Digital SST 50th to 70th percentiles range	8	104	0.00	0.01	2.54	HRSST (°C) P70-P50 = n*0.01
Digital SST 70th to 90th percentiles range	8	112	0.00	0.01	2.54	HRSST (°C) P90-P70 = n*0.01
Hydrostatic pressure (mean) offset from 10.130 dbar	12	120	-5.000	0.005	15.470	pHydr (dbar) = n*0.005 - 5
Hydrostatic pressure standard deviation	10	132	0.000	0.005	5.110	pHydr Sd (dbar) = n*0.005
Submergence/gauge count	6	142	0	1.6129	100	Subm. (%) = n * 1.6129
Battery voltage	6	148	5.0	0.2	17.4	Vbat (V) = n*0.2 + 5
Iridium SBD transmission duration	6	154	0	5	310	SBTD (s) = n*5
Iridium retries	3	160	0	1	6	SBDR = n
GNSS delay since last fix	12	163	0	1	4094	Delay (min) = n
GNSS Latitude (deg N)	21	175	-90.0000	0.0001	90.0000	Lat (deg) = n*0.0001 - 90
GNSS Longitude (deg E)	22	196	-180.0000	0.0001	180.0000	Lon (deg) = n*0.0001 - 180
GNSS number of satellites	5	218	0	1	30	Nsat = n
GNSS Time To First Fix	9	223	0	1	510	TTFF (s) = n
GNSS error radius max one-sigma	7	232	0.000	0.015	1.890	ERR (km) = n*0.015
Optional 1-Hz message indicator	1	239				1 if additional 1-Hz messages are to be sent by the buoy, 0 otherwise

Format #092 - SVP-BRST with 1 Hz sampling

(variable length)

Parameter	Bits	Pos	Offset	Slope	Max	Formula
Format identifier	8	0	0	1	254	Forced to 92
Year	7	8	2000	1	2126	Year = n + 2000
Month	4	15	0	1	12	Month = n
Day	6	19	0	1	31	Day = n
Hour	5	25	0	1	23	Hour = n
Minute	6	30	0	1	59	Minute = n
Reason for sending the 1-Hz message	8	36	0	1	255	To be documented as models are deployed
Message Sequence Number (MSN)	4	44	0	1	14	MSN = n
Max MSN	4	48	0	1	14	Max MSX = n (typically 4)
Ndata	8	52	0	1	254	Number of pairs of data points in the message (typically 75)
First Digital SST	16	60	-5.000	0.001	60.534	HRSST_1 (°C) = n*0.001 - 5
First Hydrostatic pressure offset from 10.130 dbar	12	76	-5.000	0.005	15.470	pHydr_1 (dBar) = n*0.005 - 5
...		(example below for Ndata =75)				
Last Digital SST	16	2132	-5.000	0.001	60.534	HRSST_Ndata (°C) = n*0.001 - 5
Last Hydrostatic pressure offset from 10.130 dbar	12	2148	-5.000	0.005	15.470	pHydr_Ndata (dBar) = n*0.005 - 5

The reasons for sending the SBD messages in this format can be documented with a series of 8 bits. This is to be documented as buoys are deployed.

The length of the message is equal to (7.5 bytes + Ndata * 3.5 bytes).

To transmit 5 minutes of 1 Hz data:

- Ndata=75; each message is then 270 bytes long (equivalent to 9x 30-byte invoiced blocks), and
- Max MSN=4, as 4 consecutive SBD messages are needed.

This represents a total size of 1080 bytes (equivalent to 36x 30-byte invoiced blocks).

3. Manufacturer's technical parameters

(updated on March 1st, 2017)

Manufacturer	1st parameter (Iridium - 8 bits)	2nd parameter (8 bits)	3rd parameter (GPS - 7 bits)	4th parameter (GPS - 4 bits)
DBi	Iridium SBTD	Iridium RSSI	GPS TTFF	Nb of satellites
Marlin	Iridium SBTD	Iridium SBTR	GPS TTFF	Nb of satellites
Metocean	Iridium SBTD	Iridium CSQ	GPS TTFF	GPS S/N ratio
Pacific Gyre	Iridium SBTD	Iridium SBTR	GPS TTFF	GPS Quality Flag
NKE	Iridium SBTD	Iridium SBTR	GPS TTFF (TTFF(s) = n)	Nb of satellites

Examples of manufacturer's technical parameters

CSQ: Iridium SBD Signal Quality

GPS quality flag

GPS S/N ratio

RSSI: Iridium Received Signal Strength Indication

SBTD: Iridium SBD Transmission Duration

SBTR: Number of Iridium SBD Transmission Retries

TTFF: Time to First GPS fix

CSQ = n

Flag = n

GPS S/N (dB) = n*4

SBTD (s) = n

SBTR = n

TTFF (s) = n*2